

Editorial

Ioan-Gheorghe Rotaru

Professor PhD. Dr. Habil. 'Timotheus' Brethren
Theological Institute of Bucharest, Romania
dr_ionicarotaru@yahoo.com

People are characterized by rationality, and rationality assumes the ability to think. Thinking has two sides, one informational, which reveals the content of thinking, and another operational, which reveals the functionality of thinking, the fact that it involves the transformation of information in order to acquire new knowledge or to solve problems. It is worth noting that human thinking is not uniform, but it depends on the education received in the family, in school or even through one's own efforts. Some people think that to think critically means to be grumpy, opportunistic, to reject the ideas of others just for your own ideas to be imposed. Obviously, as human beings, this ability to think is extremely important because human life is much more complex than the life of any other creature, and because of this man needs a system of thinking to help him navigate through the complexity of life, and this help comes from critical thinking, which has precisely this role.

As human beings, it is not enough just to reason about the fact that you exist, that you eat, that you have certain needs that must be met, but you need more than that. It is not enough to have certain knowledge in a certain field, but it is necessary for that knowledge to be transposed into everyday life, this being a skill that every human being needs, because the whole quality of our life depends on the quality of thinking, and critical thinking is about that, the ability to be able to understand the range of information that one is approached with every day, to be able to draw the right conclusions and to be able to analyze which information is valuable and which is not, to be able to perceive what is the motivation behind some things that happen to us and then all these conclusions that are drawn to be able to be applied in everyday life in such a way that tomorrow's life is better than today's. Critical thinking is what challenges you to research, to ask questions, to document yourself, to find alternatives. In some societies, functional illiteracy is discussed, and the role of critical thinking is precisely to overcome purely existential situations, not to be concerned only with going to work and then home, but in a world of information it is necessary

to analyze, to think about being able to discover what false information is, what true information is worth listening to and applying in life.

Critical thinking is an ability that is acquired through exercise, we, as people, being rational beings but also emotional beings its possible that certain decisions are made only in terms of an emotional situation. It is not wise for important life decisions to be made in moments of anger, rage, frustration, just as it is just as dangerous to make important life decisions only when everything is fine, when everything is rosy or better than it should be, while a man who develops rational thinking is a man who learns to effectively subject emotions to rational thinking, having a judgment as objective and clear as possible. Certain situations need to be managed very quickly, there may be an opportunity in life, you may be in traffic behind the wheel, situations that require very fast thinking at the moment, and without it you may miss an opportunity or end up in a dangerous situation. In life there are situations that require a faster or slower, more settled thinking (when it comes to career orientation, marriage, investment, choosing a job, etc.), and the big challenge is to know when to use one or the other, because if they are confused the results can be disastrous. In life it is very important to learn to think critically, objectively, because otherwise you can end up in the situation of being a victim of your whole life, of your whole society, always falling behind, with the frustration of finding that inappropriate and unwanted things always happen to you, because all our decisions are related to a certain type of thinking that we use, and the quality of life is related to the quality of thinking. In order for us people to have a quality life, we must be very good, or as good as possible in some essential moments of life when certain decisive decisions have to be made.

One of the fundamental elements of our life is precisely the philosophy of life, which like the wind, which pushes the waves, leads some in the desired direction, while others may suffer. It is very important that in a world like ours, which bombards you with information, you manage to know where to get your correct information, and of great value is the fact not only to have, to accumulate information, but to know how to use it. Critical thinking is a clear and free thinking, which developed allows us to prove that we have the ability to identify, to understand, to make logical connections, to detect certain errors of reasoning in arguments and presentations, to solve problems with high degree of difficulty, to identify the context and implications of an argument or idea, to identify and construct and understand the justifications behind opinions, arguments or beliefs, to construct new arguments and ideas based on those accumulated, to help you to always be a better version of yourself.